

Studies on 2-Thiophenylaldehyde: Condensation with Some Acyl Glycines

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Condensation of 2-thiophenylaldehyde with some reactive methylene compounds has been reported earlier¹. Acheson *et al.*² condensed *p*-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde and 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde with a series of acylglycines and prepared several new deeply coloured oxazolones with a view to ascertaining the usefulness of these aldehydes as reagents for the detection of acylglycines by paper chromatography. The formation of certain oxazolones from 2-thiophenylaldehyde or its diacetate has been studied by Yuan and Li³, Barger and Easson⁴, and Crowe and Nord⁵.

In continuation of our study on 2-thiophenylaldehyde¹, we have now prepared some new oxazolones. The acylglycines chosen were cinnamoyl-, *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-nitrobenzoyl-, 3, 5-dinitrobenzoyl-, anisoyl-, acetyl-, *o*- and *p*-chlorobenzoyl- and 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoyl-glycine. These were prepared by well-known methods. The general method adopted for the preparation of the new oxazolones is described below.

TABLE I

Name.	Formula.	M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.
2-Styryl-4-R*	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ NS	154°	40%	11.50	11.20
2-(3,5-Dinitrophenyl)-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₇ O ₆ N ₂ S	251°	35	9.24	9.29
2-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl)-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ NCIS	182°	42	10.82	11.07
2- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ NCIS	153°	35	11.30	11.07
2-(<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	172°	14	10.50	10.60
2-(<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	175°	60	10.70	10.60
2-(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl)-4-R	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₄ N ₂ S	217°	66	10.70	10.60
2-Methyl-4-R	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ NS	134°	40	17.06	16.61
2-(3,4-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-4-R	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ NS	238°	54	10.85	10.72
2-(<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl)-4-R	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ NS	200°	43	11.45	11.20

*R stands for (2'-thienyl)-5-oxazolone.

A mixture of 2-thiophenylaldehyde, (1.12 g.), cinnamoyl-glycine (2 g.), fused sodium acetate (0.8 g.), and acetic anhydride (3 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. Ethanol (5 ml) was added to the mixture and the flask was kept in ice for a few min. The solid

1. Kurien and Ittyerah, this *Journal*, 1961, **39**, 959.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3457.
3. *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **5**, 214.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2100.
5. *Nature*, 1949, **163**, 876.

separating was filtered and recrystallised from ethyl acetate in yellow needles of 2-styryl-4-(2'-thienyl)-5-oxazolone (1.1 g.), m.p. 154°.

The oxazolones obtained were mostly yellow in colour and their yields varied from 14 to 66%. The analytical results, m.p., etc. of these oxazolones are recorded in Table I.

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